

Medicinal properties of pomegranate fruit and its role in medicine

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Annotation: Pomegranate has been used for thousands of years to cure a wide range of diseases across different cultures and civilizations. It has great nutritional values and numerous health benefits. Pomegranates as a Treatment for Cancer, Osteoarthritis and Other Diseases. The pomegranate has been used in natural and holistic medicine to treat sore throats, coughs, urinary infections, digestive disorders, skin disorders, arthritis, and to expel tapeworms. However, modern research suggests that pomegranates might be useful in treating such serious conditions as prostate cancer, skin cancer, osteoarthritis, and diabetes. Studies also show that pomegranate seeds might help rid the digestive system of fats. Clinical research shows that pomegranates, when part of a healthy diet, might help prevent heart disease, heart attacks and strokes. This is because pomegranates have the potential to thin the blood, increase blood flow to the heart, reduce blood pressure, reduce plaque in the arteries, and reduce bad cholesterol while increasing good cholesterol. A decoction of seed is used to treat syphilis. Juice used to treat jaundice and diarrhoea. Juice of flower is used to treat nose bleeds. The fruit pulp and the seed are stomachic. Dried, pulverized flower buds are employed as a remedy for bronchitis

Keyword: Pomegranate, Treatment for Cancer, Pomegranate, Prevent Heart Disease, Jaundice and Diarrhoea

The word "Pomegranate" (*Punica granatum*) comes from the Latin for "fruit of many seeds." In folk medicine, the fruit's astringent properties have been used to treat various ailments (cuts, sore throats, tapeworms, dysentery, and gum disease). Pomegranate juice is marketed in the United States as a major source of antioxidant nutrients that protect against heart disease and other ailments. Recent research has focused on its potential use as a treatment for cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and various forms of cancer. The author examines those properties of the pomegranate, as well as its history and nutritional and chemical makeup. Pomegranates are believed to be native to the areas from eastern Iran through northern India says the author. More than a dozen cultivars of the fruit ("Wonderful" being the leading commercial cultivar in the United States) have been grown commercially in California's San Joaquin Valley since its introduction by Spanish settlers in the late 18th century. Pomegranates are a good source of vitamin C, providing between 10-20% of the recommended daily allowance according to one source¹ and up to 40% according to another. The potent antioxidant properties of the fruit have been attributed to its high content of soluble polyphenols. When tested in vitro on normal and colon-cancer cell lines, the juice was found to have superior antioxidant, antiproliferative, and proapoptotic effects compared with single purified active ingredients, probably the result of synergistic actions among the fruit's multiple compounds. Studies have shown that the antioxidant activity of the pomegranate flowers yielded activity two to three times the antioxidant potency of tea or red wine. The author notes research suggesting that pomegranate juice may be cardioprotective, reducing risk factors (such as cholesterol accumulation, foam-cell formation in macrophages, and oxidized low-density lipoprotein [LDL]) without affecting native LDL.

Cited by the author is an Israeli study in which 10 patients with carotid artery stenosis (advanced plaque build-up in the arteries) drank pomegranate juice and experienced reduced blood pressure, LDL oxidation, and progression of carotid lesions at 1-year and 3-year study intervals. In a randomized, double-blinded, placebo-controlled study at the Preventive Medicine Research Institute in Sausalito, CA, pomegranate juice drinkers with coronary artery disease had a 17% improvement in blood flow compared with an 18% worsening in the control group. The study team concluded that the antioxidants in the juice may help prevent the formation of fatty deposits on artery walls. In studies of the fruit's anticancer effects, pomegranate fruit extract (PFE) has been found to be chemopreventive in mouse mammary organ culture and in human breast cancer

cells in vitro.

In another study cited by the author, researchers at the University of Wisconsin in Madison found that PFE significantly reduced prostate-specific antigen levels and inhibited proliferation of aggressive human prostate cancer cells in athymic mice. Pomegranate extracts have exerted antiproliferative, antiestrogenic, and proapoptotic actions on leukemia cells as well as breast- and prostate-cancer cells. Results of studies with diabetic patients have shown that supplementing the diet with pomegranate juice had beneficial antioxidant effects on macrophages, implying that it could reduce the development of atherosclerosis. Australian researchers found that pomegranate flower extract reduced factors (hyperglycemia, hyperlipidemia, and a fatty heart) that can result in increased cardiac.

Pomegranate is a poly-vitamin, a unique fruit plant producing a wide spectrum of biologically active substances especially important in our present-day polluted environment. It helps in preventing the harmful effects of radioactive substances by producing biologically active substances. Russians, after the deadly Chernobyl tragedy, used pomegranates to reduce the effect of radioactive substances. In order to maintain the health and energy levels of astronauts, submariners and coal miners, they often consume pomegranate juice regularly. Pomegranate is loaded with tannins, anthocyanins, polyphenolics and antioxidant vitamins, A, E and C, all of which have a health effect on the body. These elements work together to benefit the arteries, plus it keeps the cardiovascular system healthy which is the chief health benefit of Pomegranate. It has also been found to increase levels of nitric oxide, which improve blood flow to the heart, reduce arterial plaque, reduce systolic blood pressure and help in curing erectile dysfunction. Other benefits include preventing premature aging, stroke, arthritis, Alzheimer's and even cancer. The juice of the red pomegranate has received attention for its rich flavor and healthboosting properties. If you cut a pomegranate open, you will see the many tiny pomegranate "arils" or seeds that are contained inside. The juice comes from the crushed seeds. Pomegranate juice has been shown to contain more antioxidants than most fruit juices, red wine or green tea, according to Health Castle

Conclusion

Punica granatum has been claimed in traditional literature to be valuable against a wide variety of diseases, such as kidney stone, bleeding of kidney, irritable condition of bladder inflammation, painful urination, burning sensation, problem in urine discharge flowers are used in diarrhea, dysentery, hyperacidity, cardiogenic, dental disorders, anemia, piles, sterility and cough.

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